

Transmission and distribution Hybrid nEtworks with enhanced resilience and robUstness

Advanced methodologies and tools supporting hybrid grids implementation across **High, Medium and Low Voltage levels**

Use cases assessed with actual data from **five distinct hybrid grids**

Solutions will be validated in **three pilot environments** across six different test benches at TRL 5

PARTNERS

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